

ROLE OF VENUS IN JEWELERS / JEWELRY BUSINESS

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Abstract:

In the nine planets of the zodiac Venus is the sixth one. Venus is the son of saint Brigu and Pilomisai. Saint Brigu is the son of Lord Brhma. So, Venus is also called as Bhrgava and also as Kavi. Venus, have Garuda (egale) as his vaahan (Vehicle). Venus is the karak for arts. He is the lord for the three stars - Ababarani, Poorva Pulguni and Poorvashada. Gold is used mostly in ornaments. If Jupiter and Venus are placed in the 4th house, or 4th lord have conjunction with the benefic planets Jupiter, Venus, the Moon and the Mercury or the 3rd lord is in the Jupiter's house or in the Venus's house or the lords of 10th and 11th houses the native will happen to do the business of gold, diamond ornaments.

Introduction:

Venus is orbits away from the Sun about 6, 70, 00, 000 kms. It orbits around the Sun in 225 days and it takes 23 and ½ hours to come around its own self. The Guru of Demon (Asura's) Venus is called as the Kalathira Karak. He is responsible for the luxurious and best life of an individual. Sexual feelings, secret organs, love, virility, jewels, well being, vehicle, dresses, decorations, fragrance, music, beauty, business, dance, 64 types of arts and acting are the other karakas of Venus. Venus has its seventh aspect. East is his direction. Athi Devata is Indhi Rani and the prethyathi Devata is Indra. The appropriate ratna for Venus is Diamond.

Description:

Venus is the devotee of Lord Shiva. By the grace of lord Shiva, Venus came to know the "Amirtha Sanjeevi Manthra" by which people come alive after death. Venus is whitish in complex and come around in Garuda Vahan (Vehicle) with white lotus flower. Crocodile is also his vahan. He is the guru of Demon and called as "Sukrachiyar". He is the lord for the signs "Taurus and Libra. The main period of Venus is 20 years. He travels a sign in a period of one month. Mercury and Saturn are the friends of Venus and the enemies are the Sun and the Moon. Equal planets are Mars and Jupiter.

The Taurus and the Libra is its own houses, exalted house if Pisces and the debilitated house is Virgo. If Venus and the Moon are placed in the 10th house, the native will shine as a best actor and he will be very lucky. For any ascendant, if Venus alone is placed in the 10th house the native will be an expert in the any branch of art and entertain people. To buy and sell some article the support of Venus is necessary. For jewelry mart Venus should be strong enough. Strong Venus confers success in the love affairs. In the main period of Venus (if strong) the native will enjoy the heavenly bliss and eroticism. The native will be called as gentleman. If a strong Venus present in the 4th house the native will acquire wealth, vehicle, dignity etc. The remedial place for Venus Dhosha is Kanjanoor near Kumbakonam. Venus should be worshiped with white lotus flower and the dress code for remedy is Blue.

Karakathwas:

Happiness, cool, success, appreciation, solace, functions, celebrations, beauty, fragrance, wishes etc are the karakas of Venus. Venus is responsible for the moment of happiness. Even though Venus is placed in debilitated sign or in the houses 6/8/12 at least little happiness is assured to the native in his life. The native will have servants, huge palace, good vehicles, ornaments, sister, wife, daughter, sister-in-law, semen, womb, universe, chin, heart, cooking, music, dance, acting, fancy store, finance, bank, singing, jewelers, loan, liquor, vet nary department, cloth merchant, love, poem, flower, sex, marriage, house, happiness, comforts, wealth, charming, sweet, addiction, handsome, secret deals, hall, cine theatre, dance theatre, ladies club, young girl, girl child, maternal relatives, money, decorative articles, costly items, cinema, television, glands, feelings, secret organs, hormones, mother's sister, flute, restaurant, mirror, statue, mattress, garland, water games, stage decoration, attraction, income through cosmetics, glass articles, cinema, makeup man, artist, mother in day time, cooing, mountain, money will be flourishing when combine with Saturn, a bunch of flowers etc.

The most brilliant planets Venus is significator of the pleasant partner viz husband, wife, or business. Also signifies beauty, modesty, virtue, affability, sincerity, fortune, artistic disposition and of literature, dance, music, poetry, amusements, pleasurable pursuits, love, marriage, gain through public affairs, friendship, sex, conjugal or domestic happiness, attraction, relationship with opposite sex. Venusians have charming eyes, beauty, average height, round face, pleasant voice, soft and sweet smile, passions, pleasure of beds, delightful, social comforts, luxury, clubs etc. Generous, good earnings and profits through partner and speculation, refined and polished nature, fond of scents, vehicles, conveyance, courage, confidence, good sportsman, good nature, humorous taste, fond of fine arts, law abiding, follower of traditions, good financier, honest, good health and smooth life, fertile imagination and attractive personality.

If Venus is afflicted it signifies less beauty, of amorous nature, immoral life, rivalry, jealousy, unsmooth life, rash and violent action, unpleasant domestic life, separation, divorce, ill reputation, scandal, loss of conveyance through accidents, death of husband, wife or partner, plurality in sexual relations, sexy, illicit relation with others, financial loss, worries, domestic downfall, falsification of accounts, litigations, debauchery, misrepresentation, legal trouble, misfortune, dishonor, disgrace and questionable conduct.

The Venus is the lord of Friday, feminine, direction south- west. Venus Owns Taurus and Libra signs, exalted in Pisces 27°, detriment houses Aries and Scorpio. Diamond stone stands for Venus. Turquoise, pink, lemon. Yellow, and blue are colours for Venus. The metals indicated are gold and platinum. The constellations ruled by Venus are Bharni, Poorva phalguni and Poorvashada. Dasa period of Venus is 20 years. Body parts signified by Venus are ovaries, eyes, generative system.

Diseases denoted by Venus are venereal diseases, carbuncles, and stone in bladder or kidney, eyes afflictions, diseases of ovaries, weakness of sexual organs, exudation of semen, Gout, Anemia troubles in cohabitation, eye discharge, throat disease, digestive trouble, sensitiveness, leucoderma, Eczema, syphilis, gonorrhoea, menstrual troubles and abortions.

In astrology Venus takes the responsibility of healing. The flow of money is ensured by Venus as we require money from the womb to cremation ground. Venus is the savior from all our troubles in our life. Cure us from all deceases and enhance our happiness in our life. All bed comforts from women are given by the grace of Venus. Romans also consider Venus as the “Temple of divine Goddess healing and balancing”. They worship Venus as their mother and the Goddess of marriage. The Athi devata (Goddess) of Venus Sri Mahalakshmi was born from the sea, like wise Romans think that their angel Venus came from the sea-foam.

The birthday of Venus falls and celebrated on the Krishna Baksha Dhasami thithi and Poosa Star day.

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| • Signification - Spouse (Kalththiram). | • Sex - Female. |
| • Place of Worship (Shethra) - Srirangam. | • Seat - Pentagon. |
| • Devatha - Lakshmi. | • Ruling House - Taurus, Libra. |
| • Athi Devatha - Indhirani. | • House of Exaltation - Pisces. |
| • Prithiyathi Devatha - Indra. | • Mooltrikon House - Libra. |
| • Flower - White Lotus. | • Friendly Signs - Gemini, Capricorn, Aquarius. |
| • Grain - Lima Beans. | • Neutral Sign - Aries, Scorpio, Sagittarius. |
| • Stone - Diamond. | • Enemy House - Cancer, Leo. |
| • Metal - Silver. | • House of Debility - Virgo. |
| • Color - White. | • Constellations - Barani, Poorva Palguni, Poorvashada. |
| • Dress - White Silk. | • Dasa Period - 20 Years. |
| • Character - Rajasam. | • Transit Duration in A Sign - One Month. |
| • Tendency - Persons of a Gentle Disposition. | • Friendly Planets - Mercury, Saturn, Dragon's Head, Dragon's Tail. |
| • Taste - Switish. | • Neutral Planets - Mars, Jupiter. |
| • Wood Offering (Samith) - Fig Tree (Aththi). | • Inimical Planets - The Sun, The Moon. |
| • Vehicle (Vahan) - Garuda (Eagle). | • Upa Graham - Indra Dhanusu. |
| • Figure - Evenness - Equal. | • Country - Kambojam. |
| • Direction - East. | • Aspect - 7 th aspect. |
| • Body Part - Face. | • Other Names - Asura Manthiri, Bhargavan, Biruhu, |
| • Mineral - Sperm, Human Seed. | • Salliyam, Silver, Sunkan, Kavi. |
| • Disease - Silethumam. | |
| • Five Elements - Water. | |

Profession of Venus - Dance, Song, Drama, Cinema, Hotel, Lodging, Marriage Hall, Travel Agency, Architect, Textiles, Jeweler, Navratna business, Goshala, Poultry, Cosmetics, scented articles etc. If Venus is in its own house or in exaltation, the native will get successes in his profession.

Astrologically who is having more influence of the planet Venus?

- The native who have the ascendant as Taurus or Libra which signs are his (Venus) own signs.
- If Venus is placed in Taurus or in Libra (in his own sign) or in his exalted house Pisces. In Virgo sign if he get Neach Banga Raja yoga when the planets Venus, the Moon and Mercury combine there.
- If the ascendant is in the stars of Venus.
- The native who have the Malaviya Yoga of Pancha Maha Purusha Yoga.
- If Venus is the Athma Karak by getting the More degrees in the Sign.
- The Venus and the Moon combination present in a horoscope for any ascendant.
- People have Venus in a Trine.
- When Venus crosses the Sun and form Sub-Vesi yoga.

Jewels and Venus - In Tamil tradition there is very much importance is given for beautiful jewels. In ancient time people were very much attracted towards the ornaments of gold and made of navaratnas. As an economical measure they started saving gold for their future. No marriage will end without the presence of golden jewels, in the Indian marriages.

History of Jewels in the Life of Tamil People:

Before the arrival of the Muslims and Europeans, Tamils were used wear just a bit of cloth in their hip and they don't cover the whole body. They thought that wearing of shirt is indecent. Instead of dress they use to wear and cover the body with all beautiful ornaments.

The Types of Ornaments:

- Jewels on the head.
- Ear rings.
- Necklace.
- Jewels on the hip.
- Bangle.
- Ring.
- Bracelet.
- Ankle Bracelet.

Bangles, ornaments on the fore head, mangal sutra, neck lace, foot rim, girdle (belt), ear rings, nose rings are some important ornaments they were wearing during the marriages.

In the manufacture of ornaments, the silver is the 2nd metal in use. This enhances one's beauty. The feelings of mind are controlled by Venus and the Moon. Metals have the power like navaratnas. Each planet represents few metals. Gold is represented by the Sun and Jupiter. Venus and the Moon represent the Silver. Copper by Mars and the Sun, zinc by Mercury, iron and lead by Saturn and Rahu respectively.

The Effects of Metals:

The Gold - Is mostly used in the ornaments and it is represented by the planets Jupiter and the Sun. It increases the energy and the life time of a man. Jupiter causes many auspicious functions in one's family. It also becomes good omen for such functions.

The Silver:

In the manufacture of ornaments, the silver is the 2nd metal in use. This enhances one's beauty. The feelings of mind are controlled by Venus and the Moon. This is very useful to those who want to increase the power / strength of the Moon.

The Copper:

This metal is represented by the planets the Sun and Mars. This helps us to keep our health in a good condition. The secrets in the shape of the ornaments and the ratnas (stones), The Stones are specially used in the ornaments, like rings, mangal sutra, ear rings, neck lace etc. These stones may be of natural or artificial one but the shape is very important according to old traditions.

Circle / Round Shape:

It is good for love and affection. It accumulate positive strengths.

Long and Slim Shape:

Generally the long and slim stone enhances creativity. During the pregnancy time, the problems are solved by the positive energy of this shape.

Square Type:

This shape increases the wealth. This enhances money position in your life.

Triangular Shape:

This helps us to protect and enhance the power/strength.

Heart Shape:

This shape enhances love and attraction in an individual's life.

Signs and the Lucky Metals:

- Aries (mesh) - Gold ornaments are good for the sign Aries. It gives the ability to get success. Gold metal and yellow stone are very lucky to the native of Aries. It is bliss to them. Silver and diamond are not good for them.
- Taurus (virushab) - Platinum is good for the native of Taurus and silver also. That will control the mind of these people. Diamond stone is also is good for them.
- Gemini (Mithun) - The metal gold and the stone emerald (green stone) are good for the increase of the native's wealth. Silver also can be used for betterment.
- Cancer (Karkatak) - The gold and silver ornaments are good for one's secured life and Pearl is very good for personality development.
- Leo (Simha) - Gold is good for this sign. The Sun's positive energy is enhanced by this metal. Platinum and Silver ornaments are not good for health. The same is with the stones Diamond and Pearl. Ruby is the best stone for Leo people.
- Virgo (Kanya) - The gold ornaments are good. The stone Emerald is good. But, Pearl and Silver should be avoided by this natives.
- Libra (Tula) - Use silver and platinum ornaments for best results. Platinum and diamond are good for health.

- Scorpio (Vrischak) - Gold ornaments are good for this native. In navratna Topaz is very good.
- Sagittarius (Dhanu) - Gold and yellow stone are good and lucky for concentration of mind. The following metal and stones are to be avoided - Silver, Diamond and Pearl.
- Capricorn (Makar) - Platinum and silver, the stones Diamond and Sapphire are good. But, Pearl should be avoided.
- Aquarius (Kumba) - It is good to wear Platinum and Silver ornaments. Diamond helps to create world achievements and for overall successes Sapphire is the best.
- Pisces (Meena) - Positive energy is acquired by using gold ornaments. Pearl for peace; use Sapphire for luck and wealth.

If the significator of wealth Jupiter and Venus are strong in a horoscope the native will be lucky enough to have more ornaments.

The planetary combinations in a horoscope and its strength decide the profession and gain success in one's life. One or more planets combination and their connection to the ascendant and the 10th house confer proper profession to the native.

The connection of Jupiter and Venus to the Dana bavamakes the native to have a financial back ground. To transfer the gold to beautiful ornaments and to sell the same the presence of Venus is very important. The position of Jupiter and Venus in the Jeweler's horoscope –

- Planet placed in the 10th house.
- The planet placed in the 10th house - the Sun and Jupiter.
- The planet aspect the 10th house.
- The star in which the 10th lord is placed.
- The 10th lord should be Venus.
- The 10th lord and the planets with it.
- The planet that aspects 10th lord.
- The strongest planet among all these planets decides the proper profession of the native.

The Results of Venus Placed in Different Houses:

- Venus in the 1st house - One will be beautiful, learned and have very good qualities. Influence of the opposite sex, healthy long life and happiness. Good friendships and affection, artistic taste, gain and success through love of opposite sex and friendship etc. Acquisition of money through music, dance, cinema, paintings etc.
- Venus in the 2nd house - Favorable financial circumstances through social activities. Gives great devoted love and love for profession, satisfaction both spiritually and materially. Goodwill and favors from others, and money usually comes readily. Social affairs, friendship, marriage, hotels, and confectionary. Will be an orator. Venus in second house ,as second lord influenced jewellery mart proprietors / jewellers
- Venus in the 3rd house - Strong liking for arts, music, literature, poetry and all pursuits for the uplift of mind and give pleasure. Have favorable mental development, of practical insight and refined nature. Good writings, gain through publications, If Jupiter aspect from the 9th house. It indicates favor from relations and neighbors, gain through journey, and successful travels. Have pleasant correspondence and social acquaintances. Have creative and resourceful mind, optimistic and cheerful.
- Venus in the 4th house - Favorable to domestic affairs, agreeable and fortune. Relations with parents will be pleasant and happiness. Gain of inheritances, conveyance, comfortable conditions, love of home and country. Popular in public and acquisition of house, property, finance and if favorably aspected by the Sun, the Moon or Jupiter indicates good fortune, success in general. Blessed with wife and children, happy, good vehicles, clothes, Jewellery and scentsetc. Profession in automobile and travels are indicated.
- Venus in the 5th house - Wealthy, wise, dutiful children, self indulgent, lack of true love for work. Gain through children. Have more girls than male children. Gain through love affairs, partnerships, charitable nature, idealistic love relations, good marriage and children. Gain through speculation, investment and amusement projects. Success through social life. Can worship Goddess Maha lakshmi. May have some Govt. job.
- Venus in the 6th house - Victory over enemies, good health, gains in employment from employer, and through subordinates and servants. Care with eating and drinking. Love of pets, clothes and small animals. Gain through pleasures.
- Venus in the 7th house - Love, affection and partnership are sources of success. Gain after marriage and social success. Happy domestic life, successful partnerships, faithful, sincere and devoted nature. Have success in public relations, enjoyment and happiness. Acquire wealth and prosperous. Related to prominent persons and clever in coition. Good wife but native will have relations with other women.

- Venus in the 8th house - Financial gain through marriage or partnership, legacy or goods and affairs of dead. Peaceful and natural death. Money or gain through marriage or partner, money should not be used in speculation or insecure investment which may not result into loss. Universal love, pure affections and cordial relations be maintained. Great interest in psychic research, occultism and enjoys long life. Rich and holds good position.
- Venus in the 9th house - Sympathetic, kind, helpful, very much esteemed for religious works. Pleasure through travelling. Optimistic. Intelligent, will command all comforts, righteous disposition, blessed with wife, friends and children. Prosperous through royal favor. Fond of fine arts, music, dance, opera etc. Social connections with learned persons. Domestic happiness, gain through relatives and friends, gainful journeys abroad. Marriage abroad or to a foreigner or to a learned one will be favourable. It also indicates honors, success, good marriage and fortune.
- Venus in the 10th house - Great desire for contact with others, connections with learned and artistic persons and the career will be favorably influenced by them. Widely renowned, honors, wealth, gain through women. Good morals, social and humorous. Gain through parents and general prosperity. Happy domestic life. The profession will be connected with things which embellish life or make more pleasant and will on the whole be lucrative especially connected with females / jewelry business, Loved by women. According to the strength of guru connection with venus and tenth house exhibits dealing in gold business / jewelers. If beneficially aspected by the Sun, Moon or Jupiter, the native will conferred with high distinction, honor and financial success. Favor from persons with authority. If by Mercury it makes the native a good writer, speaker, artist if fine arts, actor, position of trust and professions which require considerable travelling or has contacts with people. Also depends much upon the nature of sign where Venus is posited.
- Venus in the 11th house - Universal brotherhood and peace will be prominent. Learned, great wisdom, rich, merciful, will have gain and profit. Fond of company of females and endowed with comforts. Relations and gain from persons occupying important places. Noble, conservative feelings, good social contacts and nature. Gain and happiness through friends. Social success and popular. Favors from women.
- Venus in the 12th house - Inclined to romance and adventure, pleasure of beds with others. It is a difficult point in horoscope. Love for the mysterious and extraordinary cases which captive the mind. Secret love affairs or intrigues leading to enmity of women. Affection for others after marriage. Wealth and splendor. If in own house famous, wealthy but should be unaffiliated.

Conclusion:

Venus has some peculiarity among other 9 planets. For all ascendants, Venus stands in Kendra, own or in exaltation. Venus confers the type of art concern with that bava which it is connected to. If a strong Venus is in connection to the 2nd, 10th and 11th houses, the native will become the owner of jewelry shop.

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